

OMOP2OBO: Semantic Integration of Standardized Clinical Terminologies to Power Translational Digital Medicine Across Health Systems

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Abstract

Common data models have solved many of the challenges of utilizing electronic health record data, yet they do not include resources needed to make inferences that combine clinical and genomic data. Biomedical ontologies provide accurate and semantically computable representations of biological knowledge. Aligning clinical data to open biomedical ontologies (OBO) requires manual and/or semi-automated curation and domain expertise, limiting existing efforts to specific diseases and clinical data. To address these limitations, we introduce OMOP2OBO - a set of health system-wide, disease-agnostic mappings between standardized clinical terminologies (i.e. condition, medication, and laboratory measurements) and eight OBO foundry ontologies spanning diseases, phenotypes, anatomical entities, cell types, organisms, chemicals, vaccines, and proteins. We will present preliminary results to include our findings when examining the coverage of these mappings in two independent health systems. Detailed documentation and code are openly available at <https://github.com/callahantiff/OMOP2OBO>.

Research Category (please highlight or circle which category best describes your research)

Observational data standards and management, clinical characterization, population-level estimation, patient-level prediction, other (if other, please indicate)

Background

Despite significant progress in biomarker discovery¹, this promise remains largely aspirational²⁻⁶. Linking knowledge from generalized molecular data to clinical electronic health record (EHR) data will enable methodological development until molecular and clinical data are more accessible. Like clinical terminologies, computational ontologies are classification systems that provide detailed representations of a specific domain of knowledge consisting of a set of concepts and formally defined relationships⁷. Unlike clinical terminologies, ontologies are semantically computable and interoperable, which means they can be logically verified using description logics and easily integrated with other ontologies and non-ontological data including data generated from basic science and clinical research⁷.

The usefulness of mapping or normalizing clinical data to ontologies, like those in the open biomedical ontologies (OBO) foundry⁸, has been recognized as a fundamental task for the future of deep phenotyping^{7,9-11}. Existing work has largely focused on using ontologies to improve phenotyping in specific diseases (i.e. infectious¹² and rare diseases^{13,14}) and for investigation of specific biological and clinical domains (e.g. laboratory tests¹⁵ and diagnoses^{16,17}). Prior work has been largely limited to one-to-one mappings (i.e. mapping a single clinical term to a single ontology concept), and rarely includes external validation. Unfortunately, learning algorithms are not yet able to capture the complex clinical and biological semantics underlying these concepts. Until a hospital-scale resource that includes mappings between multiple clinical domains and biomedical ontologies is created and validated, automatic generation of large-scale, disease-agnostic mappings will not be possible.

To address these limitations, we have developed OMOP2OBO - a hospital-scale set of mappings between OMOP standardized clinical terminologies and eight OBO foundry biomedical ontologies spanning diseases, phenotypes, anatomical entities, cell types, organisms, chemicals, vaccines, and proteins. To verify that the mappings are both clinically and biologically meaningful, we have performed extensive validation with the help of multiple domain experts spanning molecular biology, clinical pharmacology, pediatric and adult medicine, and biomedical ontology curation. Here, we present preliminary results from examining the coverage of the mappings in two independent Institutions.

Methods

Standard clinical terminology concepts were extracted from a PEDSnet OMOP v5-normalized de-identified version of the Children's Hospital Colorado EHR. Clinical concept lists consisted of all standard terminology concept identifiers and source codes from the Condition Occurrence, Drug Exposure, and Measurements tables. Additional metadata for each concept identifier included labels and synonyms at both the concept and concept ancestor-level. Ontologies were selected under the advice of several clinicians, molecular biologists, and professional [OBO Foundry](#) biocurators and included diseases, phenotypes, anatomical entities, cell types, organisms, chemicals, vaccines, and proteins. Clinical data use was approved by the Colorado Multiple Institutional Review Board (15-0445) and all ontologies are openly available. Additional details, code, and SQL queries are available on the [OMOP2OBO GitHub Wiki](#).

Mapping OMOP Standard Clinical Terminologies to OBO Concepts

Clinical concepts were mapped at the concept and ancestor level, drug exposures concepts were mapped at the ingredient level, and measurement concepts were mapped according to their LOINC scale type. Mapping was performed using automatic and manual strategies. The automatic approach consisted of ontology database cross-reference (dbXRef) mapping, exact string mapping, and cosine similarity scoring. For dbXRefs, all clinical concept and ancestor source codes were aligned to all ontology concept dbXRefs. Exact string mapping was performed using all clinical and ontology concept labels and synonyms. Cosine similarity scoring was performed using all clinical and ontology concept labels, synonyms, and definitions. All concepts unable to be mapped automatically were manually mapped.

Validation

20% of the manual condition, drug exposure, and measurement mappings were verified by a panel of domain experts. Three to five iterations of review between the experts were performed and only completed when a consensus was reached.

Results

The full set of mapped clinical concepts included 29129 condition concepts, 1693 unique drug exposure concepts, and 1605 measurement concepts. For conditions, 20850 concepts were mapped to 4661 phenotypes and 3614 diseases. For drug ingredients, 1574 were mapped to 1422 chemicals, 91 proteins, 39 organisms, and 54 vaccines. Expanding measurement concepts by LOINC scale type yield 4358 results which mapped to 920 phenotypes, 25 anatomical entities, 27 cell types, 338 chemicals, 194 organisms, and 113 proteins. Coverage analysis of the OMOP2OBO concepts on data from two independent hospitals revealed 80-92% coverage of condition occurrence concepts, 91-96% coverage of drug exposure concepts, and 25-34% coverage of measurement concepts.

Discussion/Conclusions

We introduce OMOP2OBO, a hospital-scale set of mappings between 23,824 standardized OMOP clinical terminology concepts and 42,249 concepts in eight OBO foundry biomedical ontologies. Although evaluation is still underway, preliminary results suggest excellent coverage of OMOP2OBO condition and drug concepts and moderate coverage of measurement concepts when examined in two hospitals. Future work will include developing additional code to improve the coverage of measurement concepts as well as will include a pediatric asthma classification task designed to demonstrate the contribution of

the mapped ontology concepts.

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